

Hydrolysis probe-based real-time PCR as an SNP genotyping method: an application in pharmacogenetic study of lung cancer patients

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Received 29 December 2024 ♦ Accepted 28 June 2025 ♦ Published 6 November 2025

Citation: Ishmatullah MH, Amalia R, Barliana MI (2025) Hydrolysis probe-based real-time PCR as an SNP genotyping method: an application in pharmacogenetic study of lung cancer patients. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e145414>

Abstract

Single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) play a crucial role in determining an individual's susceptibility to diseases and influencing their response to drugs. Among the various techniques available for SNP genotyping, hydrolysis probe-based real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) has emerged as a highly sensitive and cost-effective method, offering both accuracy and specificity. This method has proven particularly valuable in lung cancer research, where its potential to advance pharmacogenetics holds immense promise. Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, with genetic variations serving as critical markers for both screening and treatment. This review examines the principles, mechanisms, and applications of probes in SNP genotyping, with a focus on method validation and quality control. Hydrolysis probes are distinguished by their high sensitivity and specificity but face challenges such as inconsistent quality control and limitations in multiplex assays. This review underscores the importance of robust validation processes in ensuring the reliability of research findings and facilitating the translation of basic studies into clinical applications. By addressing these challenges, hydrolysis probe-based SNP genotyping can significantly contribute to advancing personalized medicine, particularly in the context of lung cancer research.

Keywords

pharmacogenetic, validation, quality control, lung cancer

Introduction

Single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), the most frequently studied type of genetic variation, refer to changes in a single nucleotide base that can influence an individual's genotype or phenotype. These variations play an important role in determining a patient's response to treatment and susceptibility to disease (Oates and Lopez 2018; Robert and Pelletier 2018). SNP analysis can be performed using various genotyping techniques to determine the genetic compo-

sition of individuals. The most common methods for SNP analysis include sequencing, SNP arrays, restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP), amplification refractory mutation system (ARMS), and high-resolution melting analysis (HRMA) (Medrano and De Oliveira 2014; Kawai et al. 2015; Torkamaneh et al. 2016; Nhan et al. 2018; Hashim and Al-Shuhaib 2019). Among these, the real-time PCR-based hydrolysis probe method is highly sensitive, cost-effective compared to sequencing, and frequently used for SNP detection (Matsuda 2017; Cancino-Muñoz et al. 2019).

SNPs are widely used as markers in pharmacogenetics studies, a branch of pharmacology that focuses on the relationship between genetic variations and individual responses to drugs, including those related to cancer (Krasi et al. 2019). Lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related deaths globally and was the second most commonly diagnosed cancer, following breast cancer, in 2020 (Bray et al. 2024). In the United States, *EGFR* and *KRAS* mutations in lung cancer patients have been approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) as screening markers (Kemenkes RI 2017). One contributing factor is the presence of genetic variations, such as SNPs, which significantly influence patients' responses to pharmacotherapy (Katara 2014). Although many investigations have examined the impact of specific SNPs on lung cancer patients, there has been limited progress in the clinical implementation of new biomarkers despite advances in basic research (Sadik et al. 2022).

This gap may be attributed to differences in methodology between basic studies and clinical validation, particularly the need for more rigorous quality control in certain studies. The absence of quality control can result in less precise conclusions and hinder development at the clinical level (Goossens et al. 2015; Ou et al. 2021). Therefore, this review aims to provide an in-depth discussion of the principles of probes used for SNP genotyping, their application in basic studies, and the evaluation of validation methods.

Materials and methods

A literature search was conducted using PubMed and Google Scholar databases with a combination of keywords: "hydrolysis probe" OR "TaqMan methods" AND "SNP detection" AND "lung cancer" OR "SCLC" OR "NS-CLC." The initial search yielded 273 articles. These were subsequently screened based on inclusion criteria limited to studies involving human subjects and published within the last ten years. Duplicate entries were removed ($n = 10$). Title and abstract screening excluded 171 articles that did not meet the relevance criteria. Of the remaining studies, 41 were excluded because they did not employ hydrolysis probe-based methods, and 45 were excluded due to irrelevance to lung cancer research. Ultimately, six articles were identified as meeting all criteria and were included in the final review.

Result and discussion

Hydrolysis probe mechanism

Hydrolysis probes consist of two main components: a reporter (a fluorophore such as FAM [6-carboxyfluorescein], VIC [a proprietary dye], or HEX [hexachloro-fluorescein]) and a quencher (such as NFQ [non-fluorescent quencher], IBFQ [Iowa Black fluorescent quencher], ZEN, or MGB [minor groove binder]), which quenches the fluorescence emitted by the reporter. The reporter, or fluorophore, is a fluorescent molecule that absorbs light at

specific wavelengths and re-emits it at longer wavelengths (Nagy et al. 2017). Each reporter possesses a distinct emission wavelength that can be detected by real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) instruments (Grohmann et al. 2021). The combination of FAM and VIC reporters is commonly used in such assays (Grohmann et al. 2021). It is also important to note that the term "hydrolysis probe" is the appropriate generic descriptor, while brand-specific names such as "TaqMan probe" should be reserved for commercial use only (de Gonzalo-Calvo et al. 2022).

Hydrolysis probes are structured with a reporter at the 5' terminus and a quencher at the 3' terminus, ensuring that the fluorescence of the reporter remains undetectable until the probe undergoes hydrolysis (Artika et al. 2022). During the PCR extension phase, *Taq* DNA polymerase—characterized by its 5' to 3' exonuclease activity and absence of 3' to 5' exonuclease activity—cleaves the probe. This enzymatic cleavage separates the reporter from the quencher, permitting fluorescence emission. The emitted fluorescence is subsequently detected by real-time PCR, facilitating the specific detection of the target DNA being analyzed (Ding et al. 2024).

In SNP genotyping, the amplification of the target gene is performed in conjunction with two distinct hydrolysis probes that emit different fluorescent signals, enabling the detection of SNP variations within a single PCR reaction (Prayuni and Yuliwulandari 2022). Ongoing advancements in probe design continue to focus on improving the efficiency and performance of hydrolysis probes. One known example is the TaqMan probe, which incorporates a minor groove binder (MGB) at the 3' end (5'R --- Q3') (Xue et al. 2020). Similarly, the PrimeTime probe, designed with a double quencher system (5'R --- ZEN --- Q'3), offers increased sensitivity at a reduced cost (Hirotzu et al. 2020). The structure of the hydrolysis probe is shown in Fig. 1. However, while these probes are frequently utilized for viral detection, such as in SARS-CoV-2 diagnostics, further validation is required for their application in SNP genotyping (Hirotzu et al. 2020).

Figure 1. Structure of hydrolysis probe.

Comparison of hydrolysis probe with other methods

Hydrolysis probe-based real-time PCR has demonstrated high accuracy and specificity for SNP genotyping, as sup-

ported by previous studies (Abdurakhmonov 2018; Devi et al. 2019). In addition to its robust performance, this method is more cost-effective than sequencing techniques (Matsuda 2017; Cancino-Muñoz et al. 2019). Zhang et al. (2013) reported that Sanger sequencing involves more complex laboratory procedures and requires longer processing times. In a comparative analysis of the hydrolysis probe TaqMan and high-resolution melting analysis (HRMA), the hydrolysis probe exhibited superior accuracy, achieving a rate of 0.997 with a 95% confidence interval (CI) ranging from 0.994 to 0.999 (Zhang et al. 2013). Similarly, when comparing specificity, HRMA demonstrated a specificity of 0.995 (95% CI: 0.991–0.999), whereas the hydrolysis probe exhibited a slightly higher specificity of 0.996 (95% CI: 0.993–1.000) (Zhang et al. 2013). Additionally, the hydrolysis probe demonstrated superior sensitivity. The sensitivity for HRMA was reported at 0.996 (95% CI: 0.989–1.002), while the hydrolysis probe showed higher sensitivity at 0.998 (95% CI: 0.993–1.002) (Zhang et al. 2013).

Another example is a study aimed at detecting the presence or absence of porcine content. The hydrolysis probe was 10,000 times more sensitive than conventional PCR and 100 times more sensitive than probes using intercalating dye structures such as SYBR Green (Zhou et al. 2017). Although SYBR Green, an intercalating dye probe, is cheaper than the TaqMan brand hydrolysis probe, it tends to produce false-positive results in SNP genotyping (Xia et al. 2021; Rahmasari et al. 2024). The primary drawback of this method is the potential for false-positive signals, as the SYBR dye binds to any double-stranded DNA, including nonspecific sequences. To address this issue, careful primer design is crucial to ensure the amplification of only the target sequence while minimizing non-target amplification. Moreover, melt curve analysis is essential to ensure specificity (Pereira-Gómez et al. 2021).

Despite its advantages, the hydrolysis probe method for SNP detection has limitations. Specifically, it requires the design of multiple distinct probe sequences for each variation, which can increase assay complexity. The introduction of a second probe adds further intricacy, particularly in studies using multiplex probes for SNP genotyping. Furthermore, multiplex assays require more complex optimization, evaluation, and validation than assays using a single hydrolysis probe (Nagy et al. 2017).

Criteria for ideal primer design

The design of primers represents one of the most critical factors in determining the success of real-time PCR assays. Primer design can be conducted *in silico* using various available software and online platforms to predict key parameters such as GC content, melting temperature (T_m), and potential secondary structures that may form (Nolan et al. 2013; Kumar and Chordia 2015). The following are some of the ideal criteria for primer design: (1) The nucleotide length should range between 18 and 24 bp; (2) the melting temperature (T_m) should be approximately 60 °C (59 ± 2 °C), with a maximum difference of 2 °C between the forward and reverse primers; (3) the GC content

should be within the range of 40–60%; and (4) primers should not form secondary structures (Nolan et al. 2013).

Urgency of validation and quality control of real-time PCR-based hydrolysis probes at the research level

Method validation is a series of tests designed to determine whether a method meets the requirements to produce accurate and reliable analytical results (Bustin et al. 2009). During the biomarker discovery phase, validation is often conducted under uncontrolled and unstandardized conditions. This lack of rigorous validation leads to uncertainties that can hinder the transition of research results to clinical applications. The hydrolysis probe method used in real-time PCR for SNP detection during this discovery phase is typically classified as research use only (RUO), which does not require formal regulatory approval. As a result, the validation process at this stage is less stringent than that required for clinical diagnostic tests (de Gonzalo-Calvo et al. 2022).

Despite this, validation at the RUO stage remains essential for ensuring that research findings can be reliably translated into clinical settings. Analytical validation, commonly performed at the RUO level, focuses on evaluating key performance characteristics such as sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, precision, and inter-laboratory reproducibility (Ou et al. 2021). Ensuring that these characteristics are met is vital for guaranteeing that SNP genotyping results are both reliable and reproducible, which is essential for their later application in clinical practice.

A consensus on validation includes several key tests: positive controls should produce successful amplification, negative controls should show no amplification, and the specificity of amplification should be assessed. Additionally, testing with serial dilutions is necessary to evaluate key parameters such as linearity, efficiency, and dynamic range. These steps ensure that the assay can detect a wide range of analyte concentrations while maintaining high levels of sensitivity and accuracy (Broeders et al. 2014; de Gonzalo-Calvo et al. 2022). Testing specificity is also critical to confirm that the hydrolysis probe method can precisely detect the target SNP without interference from non-target DNA sequences, which is crucial for the reliability of results (Nagy et al. 2017).

Real-time PCR efficiency reflects how effectively the assay amplifies DNA with each cycle, which directly affects the reliability of results. Linearity, assessed using regression analysis, indicates how well the PCR response correlates with the concentration of the analyte. A highly linear response ($R^2 \geq 0.98$) and an efficiency of 90–100% are considered optimal for obtaining accurate results. The dynamic range, defined as the range of sample concentrations where the assay performs effectively, is also a key factor. This range must be adequately determined to ensure that the assay can reliably detect both low and high concentrations of the target DNA (Broeders et al. 2014).

Despite the robust theoretical basis for SNP genotyping, studies frequently encounter challenges related to reproducibility, particularly when translating research findings

into clinical practice. This variability underscores the importance of rigorous quality control and adherence to standardized protocols. Research studies associating SNPs with gene function must employ validated methodologies to ensure consistent and reliable data. Implementing protocols such as those outlined by “Nature Protocols” and the Quality Control Measurement Protocol for the Association for Genomic Studies is essential to maintain high-quality data throughout the research process (Ayday et al. 2023).

Application of hydrolysis probe at the research level of lung cancer patients

Lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer-related death worldwide, with an estimated 1.8 million deaths (18%) in 2020 (Bray et al. 2024). The disease often remains asymptomatic in its early stages, which leads to a delay in diagnosis until the cancer has progressed significantly (Gildea

et al. 2017). Lung cancer is classified into small cell lung cancer (SCLC) and non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) based on histology (Chan and Hughes 2015). The majority of lung cancer patients—approximately 85%—are diagnosed with NSCLC, which is further classified into subtypes including adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and large cell carcinoma (Zappa and Mousa 2016). *EGFR* mutations are clinically significant and have been approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for testing in patients with lung cancer. These tests utilize hydrolysis probes and have received FDA premarket approval (PMA), as indicated by the specific PMA number P120022 (U.S. Food and Drug Administration 2013).

Several SNPs that have been studied at the basic research level in lung cancer using hydrolysis probes are listed in Table 1. Of the six studies, two did not report quality control procedures, while four mentioned performing quality control, either by sequencing or by randomly re-genotyp-

Table 1. Quality control and analysis of hydrolysis probe as an SNP genotyping method and its significance in lung cancer pharmacogenetics research.

Genes	Results	Hydrolysis probe brands	Quality control	Population	Cancer type	Ref
<i>GADD45B</i> rs2024144C>T	A significantly elevated risk of severe hematologic toxicity.	TaqMan Probes	Four negative controls (without DNA <i>template</i>) were used, and samples were tested twice for quality control. The test was repeated for 5% of the samples, and the results were 100% consistent.	Chinese	NSCLC	(Jia et al. 2016)
<i>MAPK14</i> rs3804451G>A	A significantly increased risk of both overall toxicity and gastrointestinal toxicity.					
<i>GADD45A</i> rs581000G>C	A decreased likelihood of developing anemia.					
<i>GADD45B</i> rs2024144C>T	A markedly increased risk of developing leukocytopenia or agranulocytosis.					
<i>TOP2A</i> rs13695	Patients with the C/C genotype at rs13695 in the <i>TOP2A</i> gene had a lower risk of neutropenia during chemotherapy than C/T heterozygotes.	TaqMan Probes	This method was validated based on analysis performed on controlled DNA with known genotypes. The analysis did not include samples with low amplification (Ct > 35 cycles).	Caucasian	SCLC	(Nicoś et al. 2021)
<i>ERCC1</i> rs3212986	Patients with the C/C genotype at rs3212986 in <i>ERCC1</i> had a higher risk of anemia during chemotherapy than C/A heterozygotes.	TaqMan MGB Probe	Not mentioned	Egyptians	NSCLC	(Zaghla et al. 2022)
<i>ERCC1</i> rs11615	The G/A genotype at rs11615 in <i>ERCC1</i> was associated with shorter overall survival (9 vs. 12 months) compared to the A/A genotype.					
<i>ERCC1</i> rs11615	No significant association was found between the <i>ERCC1</i> rs11615 polymorphism and response to platinum-based chemotherapy in advanced non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC).	TaqMan MGB Probe	Sequencing	Han Chinese	NSCLC	(Wang et al. 2021)
<i>ERBB4</i> rs1836724	Patients with the GG genotype at rs1836724 exhibited reduced progression-free survival and overall survival.	TaqMan Probes	10% of samples were randomly selected for retesting, and 100% of the results were consistent.	Non-smoking Chinese Women	NSCLC	(Feng et al. 2017)
<i>PPP1R13L</i> rs1005165 <i>CD3EAP</i> rs967591	<i>PPP1R13L</i> rs1005165 and <i>CD3EAP</i> rs967591 may be linked to a reduced risk of NSCLC in Chinese non-smoking females, though no significant association with NSCLC survival was observed.	TaqMan Probes	Not mentioned	Not Mentioned	NSCLC	(Pérez-Ramírez et al. 2019)
<i>ERCC1</i> rs3212986 <i>XRCC1</i> rs25487	Patients carrying the <i>ERCC1</i> rs3212986-GG and <i>XRCC1</i> rs25487-GG genotypes demonstrated a significantly improved overall response rate (ORR).	TaqMan Probes	Not mentioned	Not Mentioned	NSCLC	(Pérez-Ramírez et al. 2019)
<i>MDM2</i> s1690924	Patients with the <i>MDM2</i> rs1690924-GG genotype exhibited an increased risk of mortality.	TaqMan Probes	Not mentioned	Not Mentioned	NSCLC	(Pérez-Ramírez et al. 2019)
<i>ERCC1</i> rs11615 <i>ERCC2</i> rs13181 <i>ERCC2</i> rs1799793 <i>XRCC1</i> rs1799782 <i>MDM2</i> rs1470383 <i>MTHFR</i> rs1801131 <i>MTHFR</i> rs1801133	No impact of <i>ERCC1</i> rs11615, <i>ERCC2</i> rs13181, <i>ERCC2</i> rs1799793, <i>XRCC1</i> rs1799782, <i>MDM2</i> rs1470383, <i>MTHFR</i> rs1801131, or <i>MTHFR</i> rs1801133 was observed on the clinical outcomes of platinum-based chemotherapy.					
<i>MTR</i> rs1805087 <i>SLC19A1</i> rs1051266	Individuals with the <i>MTR</i> rs1805087-A alleles and the <i>SLC19A1</i> rs1051266-AA genotype exhibited an increased risk of disease progression.					

ing several samples using the same method. In each test, there should be a positive control, an internal control, and a no-template control (NTC) (Moldovan and Moldovan 2020). According to the table, only one study reported the use of a positive control, and another listed the use of NTC (Jia et al. 2016; Nicoś et al. 2021). Validation is crucial to ensure the accuracy of test results, regardless of whether they are statistically significant. In pharmacogenetics, clinical relevance is strongly influenced by patient-specific characteristics.

“Excision repair cross-complementation group 1 (ERCC1)” rs11615, as studied in another investigation using the RFLP method with 20% of samples sequenced as controls, demonstrated significant associations between polymorphisms and platinum-based chemotherapy in patients with advanced-stage NSCLC (Kalikaki et al. 2009). These results differ from those reported by Zaghla et al. (2022), who employed a PCR-based hydrolysis probe method without specifying any quality control procedures. However, several other factors may account for differences in the results, including race, ethnicity, and sample size across studies (Ortega and Meyers 2014).

Conclusion

In conclusion, hydrolysis probe-based real-time PCR is a highly accurate and specific method for SNP genotyping, offering significant advantages over other techniques such as Sanger sequencing and HRMA. However, the clinical implementation of SNP biomarkers needs improvement due to the lack of consistent study quality control and validation practices. Implementing stringent validation protocols, including positive and negative controls, is crucial for enhancing the reliability and reproducibility of SNP studies. The application of hydrolysis probes in lung cancer studies demonstrates the method’s potential, but further standardization is required to ensure its efficacy in clinical diagnostics. Future studies should prioritize refining validation procedures to enable the seamless translation of SNP findings into clinical practice.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This study was funded by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology, Republic of Indonesia, under the Fundamental Research Scheme 2023 for MIB, contract number 3943/UN6.3.1/PT.00/2024.

Author contributions

MHI investigate and analyse the data and write the manuscript, RA design the analysis and review the manuscript, MIB concept and design the analysis, and supervise the writing of manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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